

This indicates that the slope of the plot of 'B' vs V_s changes with the change in the dielectric constant and this slope is found to be linear with 'D'. This change can be explained as follows: as a result of solute-solvent interaction, small density changes take place at the interface between the solute and solvent molecule. This density changes lead to changes in the microscopic viscosities of the solvent at the interface and thus, appear as increases or decreases in the Einstein's slope, depending on whether the microscopic viscosities is, respectively, higher or lower than the pure solvent value. As the 'D' changes i.e. decreases the divalent ions, as a result of their higher charge density, tend to induce much more structuring in the solvent at the interface and thus the microscopic viscosities of the solvent at the interface is higher than that it would be at high 'D'.

TABLE I

Salts	10%D		20%D		30%D	
	B	V_s	B	V_s	B	V_s
BaCl ₂	0.230	0.112	0.405	0.162	0.648	0.243
BaBr ₂	0.284	0.130	0.440	0.197	0.648	0.206
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	0.110	0.064	0.280	0.122	0.330	0.153
Ba(ClO ₄) ₂	0.267	0.128	0.390	0.150	0.600	0.226
MgCl ₂	0.430	0.190	0.540	0.244	0.640	0.292
MgBr ₂	0.460	0.191	0.600	0.247	0.870	0.358
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	0.380	0.161	0.420	0.195	0.500	0.216
Mg(ClO ₄) ₂	0.380	0.122	0.480	0.214	0.770	0.270
CaCl ₂	0.330	0.128	0.400	0.164	0.460	0.201
Ca(NO ₃) ₂	0.340	0.130	0.390	0.156	0.433	0.194
SrCl ₂	0.350	0.138	0.500	0.194	0.620	0.199
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	0.200	0.107	0.270	0.118	0.400	0.147
K ₂ SO ₄	0.280	0.122	0.300	0.138	—	—
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.300	0.130	0.325	0.148	0.410	0.146
MgSO ₄	0.690	0.278	0.700	0.289	—	—
ZnSO ₄	0.760	0.292	0.810	0.397	—	—
NiSO ₄	0.700	0.269	0.790	0.287	—	—

A gradual increase in viscosity and hence an increase in 'B' value is observed as the dioxane is increased (Table I). This phenomenon is obvious in terms of increasing molecular association¹¹ between water and dioxane with the formation of bigger molecules.

The values of ' V_s ' also increases with the increase in dioxane content of the solvent. This is in complete analogy with the theoretical expression. This may be interpreted in terms of hydrogen bond formation

between water and dioxane molecules. As dioxane is increased more and more hydrogen bonded dioxane-water molecules are formed resulting in increase in the value of V_s (table 1).

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Proximate and Amino Acid Composition of Some Hybrid Varieties of Rice

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RICE, a vital commodity and principal food crop providing a large portion of human sustenance to about half the world population, is a staple food in India and other Asian countries. To feed the expanding population is a tremendous task and therefore rice breeders are anxious to evolve high yielding varieties of rice to meet this challenge. It has been observed that the composition of rice varies with variety, plant-type, soil conditions, maturing, location, soil moisture and weather conditions prevalent at the time of grain filling.¹ It was therefore thought necessary to study the chemical composition of recently evolved high yielding varieties of rice grown in the State of Maharashtra.

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NOTES

Material and Methods: Eleven hybrid varieties of rice obtained from the Rice Specialist, Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Karjat, Kolaba District, Maharashtra were chosen for the present investigation. The varieties were (1) Jaya, (2) Satya, (3) Soorya, (4) Suhasini, (5) IR8, (6) TN₁, (7) K-14-7, (8) K-7-3A, (9) K-184, (10) P-60 and (11) R-68-1-1. All these varieties were dehusked by hand pounding and the brown rice so obtained was floured and the flour used for analysis.

Protein, ash, fat and crude fiber contents were determined by AOAC² methods. Total carbohydrate and reducing sugars were estimated by Cole's ferricyanide method.³ Available lysine was estimated by Carpenter's method⁴ and amino acid composition by paper chromatography method.⁵

Results and Discussion

Table 1 represents the proximate and available lysine composition of these varieties. Protein content varied from 6.16 to 8.10% being highest for Satya and lowest for P-60. Raghavaiah and Kaul⁶ analysed Basmati and TN₁ for protein content and found as 8% and 12.1% respectively. Raghavaiah et al¹ did so for Basmati, Jaya and IR8 and reported the same as 10.5%, 8%, 8% respectively. Protein content reported by Mitra and

Das⁷ for IR8 and TN₁ was 10.06% and 13.21% respectively. The protein content of Jaya, IR8 and TN₁ in this investigation was 7.7%, 7.9% and 7.4%. It is evident from these observations that the same variety differs in its protein content. This may be due to region, cultivation, growth conditions, fertilisers, soil and other factors.

Amino acid composition is presented in Table 2. FAO⁸ reference pattern of amino acid requirements and Eggum⁹ amino gram for rice have been given for comparison. It is clear from these results that all the essential amino acids are present in these varieties. Available lysine (Table 1) was found to be about 60 to 70% of total lysine. Among these varieties Satya and Soorya had a very high content of available lysine. Essential Amino Acid Index¹⁰ (E.A.A.I.), Biological Value¹¹ (B. V.) and Chemical Score¹² were calculated from the essential amino acid composition of these varieties and presented in Table 3. E.A.A.I. varied from 68.42 to 85.53 being highest for R-68-1-1 and lowest for TN₁. The B. V. ranged between 62.88 and 81.52 and was highest for R-68-1-1 and lowest for TN₁. The chemical score varied from 50.01 to 64.28 being highest for R-68-1-1 and lowest for P-60. It is clear from the above discussion that R-68-1-1 variety is biologically superior to all other varieties on the basis of E.A.A.I., B. V. and Chemical Score.

TABLE 1—PROXIMATE COMPOSITION AND AVAILABLE LYSINE CONTENT OF RICE

		(on wet basis)						
No.	Variety	Protein %	Fat %	Ash %	Total Carbohydrate %	Crude fiber %	Reducing sugar %	Available lysine*
1.	Jaya	7.70	1.50	0.98	79.55	0.80	0.42	2.41
2.	Satya	8.10	1.60	1.06	79.54	0.90	0.37	3.02
3.	Soorya	7.50	1.35	1.00	79.64	0.95	0.34	2.80
4.	Suhasini	6.90	1.45	1.02	76.78	0.80	0.41	3.04
5.	IR8	7.90	1.20	1.02	79.50	0.87	0.36	1.68
6.	TN ₁	7.40	1.35	1.09	76.70	0.81	0.43	2.10
7.	K-14-7	6.50	1.55	1.40	76.80	0.75	0.44	2.71
8.	K-7-3A	7.70	1.25	1.20	76.67	0.91	0.38	2.05
9.	K-184	6.20	1.50	1.40	79.65	0.87	0.45	2.80
10.	P-60	6.16	1.74	1.20	76.68	0.79	0.42	2.61
11.	R-68-1-1	6.90	1.65	1.41	78.70	0.75	0.39	2.61
	Mean	7.16	1.47	1.16	78.21	0.84	0.42	2.53
	S. D.	0.54	0.16	0.16	1.35	0.06	0.04	0.44

* in grams per 16 grams of nitrogen.

TABLE 2—AMINO ACID COMPOSITION OF RICE

(grams per 16 grams of nitrogen)

No. Variety	CYS	LYS	ASP	ALA	TRY	HIS	GLY	TYR	PHE	ARG	THR	PRO	VAL	ISO	SER	GLU	MET	LEU
1. Jaya	1.72	4.70	6.97	4.54	0.78	2.08	5.46	2.75	4.55	7.54	3.90	5.72	4.55	5.11	4.62	18.85	1.82	7.05
2. Satya	1.90	3.56	7.65	4.60	1.08	1.78	6.40	2.54	4.45	6.64	3.81	4.15	3.99	5.08	5.08	19.78	2.17	5.80
3. Soorya	2.45	3.99	7.20	4.50	0.80	1.50	6.65	4.18	4.66	6.94	4.33	4.92	5.56	5.98	5.32	20.22	1.50	6.70
4. Suhasini	2.57	4.02	7.58	5.11	0.60	1.58	7.84	3.36	2.74	7.94	4.20	4.12	4.90	5.25	4.97	22.40	1.96	7.35
5. IR8	1.77	3.62	8.53	4.83	0.76	1.44	7.10	3.31	3.56	7.11	4.57	4.45	4.58	5.08	5.94	20.32	2.24	7.10
6. TN ₁	2.53	3.64	9.18	5.21	0.59	2.06	5.75	2.88	3.84	7.95	4.17	5.19	4.29	4.75	6.85	20.55	1.51	6.40
7. K-14-7	2.25	4.30	10.13	4.90	0.90	1.66	7.50	3.15	5.25	8.70	4.50	4.62	5.76	5.70	6.60	22.50	2.10	7.43
8. K-7-3A	1.81	4.05	7.02	4.80	0.78	1.95	6.37	2.73	4.10	6.79	4.29	4.55	4.55	5.20	5.72	19.50	2.12	6.55
9. K-184	1.68	4.03	9.33	5.82	0.87	2.18	7.27	4.35	4.31	8.41	4.80	4.27	6.25	6.54	5.80	21.90	2.03	7.33
10. P-60	1.72	3.99	8.10	5.70	1.02	1.64	7.25	3.49	3.83	8.43	4.61	6.53	4.78	6.50	5.60	21.81	1.55	7.40
11. R-68-1-1	2.28	4.50	8.44	5.30	1.13	2.47	7.98	3.96	6.53	7.57	3.61	4.87	6.09	7.25	5.80	21.76	1.57	7.19
Mean	2.06	3.64	8.20	5.03	0.85	1.85	6.87	3.61	4.40	7.64	4.25	4.85	5.25	5.68	5.65	20.87	1.85	6.94
S. D.	0.34	0.55	0.97	0.46	0.17	0.33	0.79	0.59	0.84	0.69	0.35	0.70	0.72	0.69	0.63	1.00	0.29	0.52
FAO ^a	2.0	4.2	—	—	1.4	2.4	—	—	2.8	2.0	2.8	—	4.2	4.2	—	—	2.2	4.8
Eggum ^b	1.30	3.49	8.23	5.11	0.60	2.24	3.88	5.09	5.22	7.81	3.25	—	5.43	4.46	4.40	17.18	2.07	7.95

ABBREVIATIONS—

CYS—Cystine, LYS—Lysine, ASP—Aspartic acid,
 ALA—Alanine, TRY—Tryptophan, HIS—Histidine,
 GLY—Glycine, TYR—Tyrosine, PHE—Phenylalanine,
 ARG—Arginine, THR—Threonine, PRO—Proline,
 VAL—Valine, ISO—Isoleucine, SER—Serine,
 GLU—Glutamic acid, MET—Methionine, LEU—Leucine.

TABLE 3—ESSENTIAL AMINO ACID INDEX, BIOLOGICAL VALUE AND CHEMICAL SCORE OF RICE PROTEINS

No.	Variety	E.A.A.I.*	B.V.**	Chemical Score***
1.	Jaya	72.63	67.44	61.44
2.	Satya	70.52	65.17	50.86
3.	Soorya	74.94	69.58	57.01
4.	Suhasini	72.71	67.55	57.42
5.	IR8	70.78	65.45	51.71
6.	TN ₁	68.42	62.88	52.00
7.	K-14-7	76.91	72.13	61.44
8.	K-7-3A	72.26	67.06	57.85
9.	K-184	82.56	78.29	57.57
10.	P-60	75.18	70.25	50.01
11.	R-68-1-1	85.53	81.52	64.28
	Mean	74.77	69.76	56.51
	S. D.	4.63	5.40	4.58

$$*E.A.A.I. = \sqrt[n]{\frac{Lys_p}{Lys_s} X \frac{Try_p}{Try_s} X \dots X \frac{His_p}{His_s}}$$

where p refers to food protein (rice protein), s is the std. protein (egg protein) and n is the number of amino acids viz. (1) Lysine, (2) Threonine, (3) Histidine, (4) Isoleucine, (5) Tryptophan, (6) Valine, (7) Leucine, (8) Arginine, (9) Methionine + Cystine and (10) Phenylalanine + Tyrosine.

**B.V. = 1.09 (E.A.A.I.) - 11.7.

***Chemical Score is the % of most limiting amino acid (Lysine) in the protein as compared to the requirement pattern given by Rama Rao et al.¹²

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Studies in the Oxidation of Propane 1 : 2 Diol by Acid Dichromate

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AN attempt has been made to establish the steps in the oxidation of propane 1 : 2 diol by acid dichromate and the steps of reduction of dichromate in the same reaction potentiometrically. The diol loses 2, 4 and 6 electrons to give stable products (formaldehyde + acetaldehyde, formic acid and acetic acid). Formic acid is further oxidized to CO₂ only in strong sulphuric acid or in weaker acid (3N) after prolonged storage at room temperature (12-15 days).

The reduction of Cr(VI) to Cr(III) also takes place through steps of Cr(V) and Cr(IV). The latter reacts only slowly with the diol and is destroyed only after many hours.

Experimental

In these potentiometric 'titrations' we used 15.0 ml M/30 propane 1 : 2 diol in the cell and M/10 Cr(VI) in the burette. In reduction experiments the concentrations were interchanged. One would require 1.0 ml Cr(VI) to remove two electrons per molecule diol. In the reduction of H₂Cr₂O₇ → 2 Cr(III) one would require 3.0 ml diol if the diol is oxidized to formic acid + acetic acid only. If the formic acid formed is oxidized to CO₂ and water the Cr(VI) requirement would be 4.0 ml.

We followed the potentials over long periods up to 20 days. The procedure is fully described in earlier papers^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

Some of the results are given in Figs. 1 to 4. From our results we find that the diol (R) loses electrons one at a time in the following sequence,

